

Моделирование процесса научно-методического сопровождения профессионально-языковой подготовки студентов – будущих учителей русского языка как иностранного в Центральноафриканской Республике

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Обновление вектора отношений между Российской Федерацией и Центральноафриканской Республикой актуализировало проблемы поддержки системы преподавания русского языка в зарубежной образовательной среде. Эффективность этого процесса во многом зависит от грамотно организованного процесса научно-методического сопровождения обучающихся – будущих учителей русского языка как иностранного.

Цель исследования – теоретическое обоснование и разработка содержания, форм и методов научно-методического сопровождения профессионально-языковой подготовки студентов – будущих учителей русского языка как иностранного в ЦАР.

Материалы и методы. В качестве материалов в процессе исследования используется информация из российских и зарубежных научных источников (статей) и нормативных документов, в которых нашли отражение вопросы научно-методического сопровождения профессиональной подготовки будущих учителей. В исследовании использовались информационно-аналитический и сопоставительный анализ теоретических взглядов ученых на поиск стратегий научно-методического сопровождения профессиональной подготовки будущих учителей, методы теоретического обобщения, а также методы научной интерпретации.

Результаты исследования. Уточнено понятие научно-методического сопровождения профессионально-языковой подготовки учителя, теоретически обоснована необходимость создания современной модели научно-методической поддержки зарубежных обучающихся в овладении русским языком как иностранным. Разработана модель научно-методического сопровождения профессионально-языковой подготовки учителя в условиях внеязыковой среды; определены подходы, принципы, условия ее успешного функционирования. Описана технология научно-методического сопровождения, предусматривающая повышение качества профессионально-языковой подготовки учителя русского языка как иностранного, реализуемая в разных форматах в зависимости от целей и образовательных потребностей субъектов образовательного процесса.

Заключение. Проведенное исследование вносит вклад в методику преподавания русского языка как иностранного. Разработанная модель научно-методического сопровождения профессионально-языковой подготовки будущих учителей русского языка как иностранного имеет универсальный характер, обладает прикладным значением и может быть использована при обучении обучающихся-инофонов русскому языку.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

процесс обучения, модель, русский язык как иностранный, научно-методическое сопровождение, методическое обеспечение

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Modeling the process of scientific and methodological support for professional language training of students – future teachers of Russian as a second language in the Central African Republic

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The renewed focus on relations between the Russian Federation and the Central African Republic has highlighted the need to support Russian language teaching in foreign educational environments. The effectiveness of this process largely depends on the well-organized scientific and methodological support of students – future teachers of Russian as a second language.

The purpose of the research is to provide a theoretical justification and development of the content, forms and methods of scientific and methodological support for the professional and linguistic training of students – future teachers of Russian as a second language in the Central Asian Republic.

Materials and methods. The research uses information from Russian and foreign scientific sources (articles) and regulatory documents, which reflect the issues of scientific and methodological support for the professional training of future teachers. The study used information-analytical and comparative analysis of the theoretical views of scientists on the search for strategies for scientific and methodological support for the professional training of future teachers, methods of theoretical generalization, as well as methods of scientific interpretation.

The results of the study. The concept of scientific and methodological support for professional and linguistic teacher training is clarified, and the need to create a modern model of scientific and methodological support for foreign students in mastering Russian as a second language is theoretically substantiated. A model of scientific and methodological support for professional and linguistic teacher training in a non-linguistic environment has been developed; approaches, principles, and conditions for its successful functioning have been identified. The technology of scientific and methodological support is described, which provides for improving the quality of professional and linguistic training of teachers of Russian as a second language, implemented in different formats depending on the goals and educational needs of the subjects of the educational process.

Conclusion. The study contributes to the methodology of teaching Russian as a second language. The developed model of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of future teachers of Russian as a second language is universal in nature, has practical value, and can be used in teaching Russian to students with non-native speakers.

KEYWORDS

learning process, model, Russian as a second language, scientific and methodological support, methodological support

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INTRODUCTION

The issue of education is a matter of the future development of the country. The UNESCO Incheon Declaration on the Development of Education until 2030 pays special attention to the problem of teacher training and increasing the number of qualified teachers, especially in "least developed countries and small island developing States" [1]. This task can be achieved, among other things, through international cooperation.

The issues of developing and strengthening international cooperation in the field of education and the implementation of vocational training programs in the light of current challenges and changes have been reflected in a number of other international documents [2].

One of the important aspects contributing to the expansion and deepening of cooperation in the field of education between Russia and foreign countries, in particular with the Central African Republic, is the teaching of the Russian language and the systematization of organizational and methodological support for the process of training specialists in teaching Russian as a second language in universities of the CAR.

The training of specialists in Russian as a second language is also actualized by the tasks reflected in the strategic development documents of the Russian Federation, which declare the need to expand and deepen mutually beneficial cooperation in the field of education, science and culture between Russia and foreign countries [3].

The creation of open education centers and the planned construction of Russian-language schools in the Central African Republic necessitate the intensification of work on linking educational development plans in order to deepen practical cooperation between the Russian Federation and the Central African Republic and increase the level of interaction between the countries. Professional contacts play a significant role in the development of cultural dialogue between Russia and Africa. The establishment of economic, trade, scientific, and logistical links creates a significant need for specialists with good knowledge of the Russian language. Improving the quality of professional training of future Russian language teachers in universities is an important element of conducting a dialogue of cultures at a qualitatively new level in the context of digitalization of education.

The results of the project "Formation of motivation of students of the Central African Republic to learn the Russian language: theory and practice" implemented in 2023. Agreement No. 073-03-2023-043/3 dated 11/9/2023", revealed a shortage of research on the theory and methodology of teaching Russian as a second language in the Central Asian Republic, as well as problems with the introduction of innovative technologies into the learning and teaching of Russian language and computer science in the context of digitalization of education. All this indicates the relevance of the topic of the proposed project, which requires further development of scientific and theoretical content that examines certain aspects of the problem of linguistic and scientific and pedagogical support for the professional training of teachers of Russian as a second language in universities of the Central Asian Republic. At the same time, the lack of theoretical research addressing the problem of scientific and pedagogical support for the professional training of teachers of Russian as a second language in the higher school of the Central Asian Republic leads to the following contradictions:

- at the socio-professional level – between the needs of the developing labor market for specialists with knowledge of the Russian language and the insufficient level of training of students, future teachers of the Russian language;
- at the innovation and methodological level – between the need of universities in the Central African Republic for methodological innovations in order to improve the quality of language education of future Russian language teachers and the insufficient theoretical and applied justification of the content and technologies of pedagogical support for the introduction of modern technologies into the practice of teaching Russian as a second language in the context of digitalization of education;
- at the scientific and technological level – between the need to create new developments in the field of teaching Russian, including at the level of interaction with Russian colleagues, specialists in Russian as a second language, and the lack of optimal forms of pedagogical interaction in a situation of low levels of student exchange and scientific mobility.

- at the personal-motivational level – between the need to study Russian as a second language in universities and the shortage of teaching staff capable of teaching Russian as a second language at a high linguistic and methodological level.

These discrepancies highlight the relevance of this study, which focuses on the content and technologies of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of Russian teachers at universities in the Central African Republic in the context of digitalization of education. The core category of our study is "scientific and methodological support." Although this term has been used in science for decades, there is no generally accepted definition. This is primarily due to the fact that the issue of scientific and methodological support is considered at various levels of the education system. On the one hand, scientific and methodological support is declared in processes aimed at modernizing the education system and involves the development of relevant materials (regulatory, legal, scientific and methodological), monitoring the progress of implementation and providing information support, as well as promoting key educational development ideas to gain the support and involvement of experts and the general public [4]. On the other hand, within the context of achieving specific educational goals, the term "scientific and methodological support" is associated with practical activities (forms, methods, principles, conditions, technology, etc.) for achieving the stated objectives. The word "accompany" means to go along with someone or something as a companion, guide, or to show the way; to be constantly present during a journey or following; to give advice, send wishes, comments, advice, etc., following, catching up with (someone walking), etc [5].

As can be seen from the definition, the support process presupposes the activity of the support subjects and the activity-based nature of their interaction, the dynamics of the process, providing subjects with the necessary resources to avoid or overcome difficulties.

All these characteristics are reflected in the definition of "scientific and methodological support" given by Russian researchers. For example, E.A. Chiganova et al. consider scientific and methodological support as an activity aimed at "resolving the contradiction between the presence of a problem in a teacher's professional activity and the unawareness of the causes of this problem, as well as the teacher's lack of ways and means to independently resolve it" [6, p. 9].

M.A. Varzanova views scientific and methodological support as both a process and a technology. On the one hand, it is a process of interaction between support subjects, containing a set of targeted, consistent actions that help teachers successfully master innovations, develop professionally, and overcome professional difficulties. On the other hand, it is a technology of interaction between subjects, aimed at the voluntary and conscious involvement of participants in the educational process and including a set of actions to understand new ideas, actualize professional development, and successfully master the innovation [7].

G.A. Ignatyeva points to the activity-based nature of scientific and methodological support for the learning process. She believes that scientific and methodological support influences the expansion of the range of students' various talents, the development of the ability to effectively apply acquired knowledge, and the ability to work in a team, while creatively using available technologies and resources [8].

It is worth noting that, along with the term "support", the scientific literature also uses the terms "support", "coaching", "mentoring", "help", "tutoring", the main idea of which is for the teacher to provide educational, instrumental, emotional or evaluative assistance to the student [9]; creating conditions for personal results, increasing motivation for learning and forming a conscious life position of the student, perceived as an equal partner possessing internal knowledge in the form of potential [10; 11]. However, we believe that the process of support presupposes activity within the framework of each of the specified procedures, although it is not synonymous with any of these words. The use of new methods and approaches helps students themselves to build logical and cause-and-effect relationships, stimulates the search for answers and solutions, provides scope for ideas and creativity. The teacher helps students to manifest their own position, increasing activity, awareness and responsibility in the process of acquiring knowledge (Ibid.)

In accordance with the challenges of the times, the level of development of pedagogical and digital technologies, resources for professional interaction, as well as the experience of cooperation with foreign scientific and pedagogical personnel, the formats, content, directions, conditions, principles, etc. of interaction between participants in scientific and methodological activities are being updated [12].

Scientific and methodological support for teaching Russian as a second language has its own specific features and has been reflected in numerous studies by Russian and international scholars, with varying interpretations. For example, in the work of M.G. Kulaeva and P.A. Yakimov, comprehensive scientific and methodological support for teachers and students is understood as pedagogical support, revealing its essence. The authors developed a pedagogical support program and defined the principles for its construction for the purpose of teaching Russian language and Russian culture without immersion in the language environment. These principles include: the principle of consistency, professional development, individualization, interactive interaction, social responsibility, etc. Pedagogical support is interpreted by researchers as a means of fostering sustainable motivation for learning Russian language and culture [13].

In a non-linguistic environment, most researchers note the importance of the linguacultural approach in the methodological support of the process of teaching Russian to foreigners [14; 15].

It has been determined that the use of authentic songs, cartoons, films, Russian fairy tales, proverbs and sayings, etc. [14]; reading works of Russian literature [15], is a basic element in the formation of the linguacultural competence of foreign students and contributes to the improvement of their speech culture. The system of mastering the values of Russian culture in the process of teaching Russian as a second language will be successful only if certain conditions are met, namely, taking into account: 1) the similarities and differences between Russian and national cultures [14]; 2) the characteristics of autochthonous languages and cultures and their key values in the process of mastering the values of Russian culture [16]. In addition, according to scientists, the following should be taken into account: 1) the cultural and educational situations in partner countries; 2) specific conditions of regional and national academic systems [16]; 3) characteristics of the target group [14].

Given the complexity, polystructure, and multi-purpose content of the process of teaching Russian as a second language, researchers [17] are considering online methodological support, focusing on all subjects of the educational process (teacher and student), in order to systematize and improve the educational process. The main problems hindering high-quality teaching of Russian as a second language online lie in the area of developing communicative competence, the lack of a Russian-language environment, and the organization of monitoring difficulties in the development of students' written skills [18].

New formats and technologies of support are in the field of view of foreign researchers. Traditional methods, in their opinion, often fail to cope with satisfying the diverse needs of subjects of the educational process, therefore many studies consider the processes of integration of innovative pedagogical approaches in teaching a second language to native speakers of other languages. These include the use of augmented reality technology in the learning process [19]; artificial intelligence [20; 21]; various applications for language learning; virtual classrooms and interactive multimedia tools [22]; the possibility of using chatbots to optimize language learning processes [23; 19]; the use of podcasts as a technological tool for developing students' communication skills [24].

It has been established that innovative methods and educational technologies have a number of advantages: they promote better memorization, development of motivation of students, offer more opportunities for teachers in terms of individualization and differentiation, allow personalization of training [21], promote the acquisition of social experience as a result of the active activity of the subject [19]; develop critical thinking [22]; communicative competencies of students [24]; and contribute to an increase in the level of self-efficacy of the student [25].

However, researchers note a number of problems associated with the level of technological literacy of subjects of the educational process [26], the availability of platforms and specially developed materials for the implementation of the support process [19]; the creation of platforms and the definition of the functions of chatbots in the educational process [27]; ensuring high-quality control of the execution of tasks for all types of speech activity [18].

Considering the positive and negative consequences of online learning support, a number of researchers advocate a blended format that ensures a balance between autonomy and collaboration in the learning process [28]. It is noted that when creating modern means of teaching Russian to foreign speakers, one should rely on the principles of pedagogical design, the implementation of which allows for an effective learning process that takes into account the communicative needs of the target student population (Ibid.).

As an analysis of the conducted studies shows, the works describe individual aspects of scientific and methodological support, but a comprehensive picture of how this should be implemented in practice is lacking. The lack of systematicity, the predominant use of traditional forms of methodological support, and the overall lack of scientific and theoretical development in this area require a more thorough analysis and the search for new, effective methods of organizing it.

We support the opinion of researchers who believe it is necessary to create a modern model of scientific and methodological support for foreign students in mastering Russian as a second language [29].

The proposed model should take into account: a) the specific features of studying Russian as a second language; b) the goals and conditions of studying Russian as a second language typical for the partner country; c) the main methods of mastering the Russian language outside the Russian educational space (independent study, distance/blended learning, etc.); insufficient provision of foreign students with modern, high-quality means of mastering Russian as a second language, including those developed in a computer/online format; improving the quality of professional and pedagogical training of foreign teachers of Russian with the use of distance technologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research utilized the following materials: the UNESCO Final Declaration on Education Development towards 2030, the UNESCO Strategy for 2022-2029, fundamental Russian documents reflecting state national policy issues, information from Russian and international scientific sources (articles), and regulatory documents discussing scientific and methodological support for the professional training of future teachers. The study utilized information-analytical and comparative analysis of scholars' theoretical views on strategies for scientific and methodological support for the professional training of future teachers, methods of theoretical generalization, and methods of scientific interpretation.

The study was conducted on the basis of intercultural, activity-based, communicative, and cognitive approaches.

RESULTS

Understanding the process of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of a student – a future teacher of Russian as a second language in the Central Asian region in its entirety requires turning to modeling, "since only it will make it possible to see all the interrelations that exist between the parts of the system" [30]. The task is to build a model that is similar in all parameters to the proposed support process. Consequently, the model should reflect the functioning of the process of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of a student quite fully. We adhere to the point of view of V.B. Tsarkova, who believes that "all parts of the system, as well as the necessary connections between them, must be described. Only in this case can a solution be found to the problems arising both at the level of theory and at the level of technology." (Ibid.). Consequently, the model of scientific and methodological support should include the theoretical level of the professional language training of a student - a future teacher of Russian as a second language and the technological level.

The theoretical component of the model includes approaches, principles, and conditions for constructing the model. The proposed model of scientific and methodological support is based on intercultural, activity-based, communicative, and cognitive approaches.

The intercultural approach ensures the training of future teachers of Russian as a second language based on the mutual influence of the two countries' cultures, the study of the cultures and mentalities of Russia and the partner country, and presupposes the development of individuality through intercultural cooperation [31].

T.U. Tuchkova notes that "intercultural cooperation is a condition for the further peaceful development of the cultures of various peoples, as well as one of the conditions for the development of the individuality of each person in a multicultural world." The concepts of "intercultural

cooperation" and "individuality development" simultaneously act as "goals and conditions in relation to each other" [31, p. 1]. The strategy for the professional language training of students – future teachers of Russian as a second language – is the development of their individuality in intercultural interaction and cooperation based on a specially created educational environment.

The activity-based approach (A.G. Asmolov, L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, and others) provides a set of demonstrated professional actions by students, implying active participation in the educational process, a high degree of independence, and the implementation of various activities related to solving a given problem and influencing the development of personality, social norms, and professional qualities.

The communicative approach focuses on the communicative analysis of the reality of the material and spiritual world in accordance with the traditional cultural values of the native country and the country of the target language, as well as self-perceptions of oneself as a citizen of one's country.

The cognitive approach is responsible for the development of analytical and synthetic skills for critically understanding linguistic and cultural knowledge, acquiring and expanding knowledge about the worldview of representatives of various linguacultural communities.

The content of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of future teachers of Russian as a second language is developed on the basis of state documents regulating the process of teaching Russian as a second language and involves:

- understanding the values and traditions of the two countries, their interpenetration, and the search for cultural and linguistic parallels;
- taking into account the specifics of the subject component of the activity of a Russian specialist, that is, mastering the system of linguistic knowledge about the basic phonetic, lexical, grammatical, word-formation phenomena, spelling and punctuation, about the patterns of functioning of the Russian language, its functional varieties;
- the generation and understanding of oral and written texts in Russian in relation to the main functional styles in formal and informal communication;
- implementation of interlingual and intercultural interaction in oral and written forms in both general and professional spheres of communication.

Therefore, the content of education must include the indigenous cultural values of the native country and the spiritual and moral values of the country of the language being studied, which have differences, commonalities and universalisms, "possessing sufficient educational potential for the process of cognition, development, education and learning" [32]. In the process of professional language training of students - future teachers of Russian as a second language in a non-linguistic environment, intercultural cooperation is aimed at:

- orientation in the cultural values of Russia and the values of native culture (objects) and relations between Russia and the native country (knowledge);
- development of the ability to carry out speech activity, communication, educational activity (development);
- preservation and dissemination of cultural values of Russia, without violating the systemic nature of native culture, the formation of a positive image of Russia and one's country (education);
- mastery of all types of speech activity and the subject component of the activity of the future foreign language teacher as means of communication (teaching).

The following methodological principles can be used as the basis for scientific and methodological support of the process of professional language training of students – future teachers of Russian as a second language.

1) Principles of individualization and cooperation. Individualization is considered by the authors as "taking into account the individual characteristics of students, relying on their individuality and its

purposeful development in independent individual activities in the classroom and at home in various forms of cooperation," and cooperation as "socially oriented, purposeful interaction and mutual influence of individuals [31, p. 2]. Despite the fact that the process of mastering Russian as a second language is individual, it is carried out under the external guidance of a teacher and is impossible without cooperation with other students.

2) The principles of relying on the present of students and the principle of taking into account the future needs of students in intercultural interaction. When organizing scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of students – future teachers of Russian as a second language – it is essential to consider their age and individual characteristics and needs in the process of mastering Russian. It is necessary to rely not only on the students' current abilities but also on their potential and future needs, which will become a reliable prerequisite for deep creative work in mastering Russian as a second language.

3) Principles of emotional comfort in learning and mental activity. It is common knowledge that emotional and logical aspects of thinking are closely linked in the process of mastering a second language. Therefore, when teaching foreign language material, it is necessary to formulate tasks in such a way as to evoke mental and verbal activity, as well as emotional empathy, in learners. The dynamics and nature of verbal and mental activity are determined by motive. L.S. Vygotsky, revealing the nature of the speech process, wrote: "Thought is not the final authority in this entire process. Thought itself is born not from another thought, but from the motivating sphere of our consciousness, which encompasses our desires and needs, our interests and impulses, our affects and emotions. Behind thought lies an affective and volitional tendency. Only it can provide an answer to the final 'why' in the analysis of thinking. ... A true and complete understanding of someone else's thought becomes possible only when we uncover its active, affective-volitional underlying cause" [33, p. 379]. Comfortable learning can also be ensured by the principle of redundant speech material, whereby the learner has the opportunity to choose from a range of offered materials the one that is of particular interest to them. At the same time, it is necessary to specify the minimum that the learner must master. This way, not only active vocabulary is developed, but also passive and individual vocabulary.

4) Principles of communication and intercultural orientation. Communication as the initial principle of teaching Russian as a second language is that the learning process will be built adequately to the communication process in conditions close to the conditions of real speech communication, that is, in conditions of personal individualization, functionality, situationality and heuristics. The process of interacting with the facts of native and other cultures in the learning process, their comparison, juxtaposition and juxtaposition ensures intercultural orientation while maintaining one's national mentality.

5) Principles of complexity and dominance. When supporting the professional language training of students – future Russian language teachers – it is important to focus on teaching some type of speech activity in conjunction with other types of speech and non-speech activities. Particular attention should be paid to reading, as text is not only a support for speaking or writing, but also a means of cultivating a culture of value orientation, behavior, communication and work, personal qualities, etc.

These principles are binary and represent dialectically interrelated pairs. Depending on the stage and conditions of learning, the characteristics of the learners, and other factors, one or the other binary principle "outweighs".

For the successful functioning of scientific and methodological support for the process of professional language training of future teachers of Russian as a second language, conditions have been defined:

- organization of the process of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of future Russian language teachers based on intercultural, activity-based, communicative, and cognitive approaches;
- taking into account the absence of a Russian-language learning environment, the Russian educational space, and the presence of significant cultural differences between Russia and the partner country;

- taking into account the nationally determined linguistic, methodological, and cultural characteristics of teaching Russian as a second language in the partner country; foreign students and teachers are considered as a single ethnic group with a common activity, mentality, cultural, and educational base, which requires forecasting and taking into account not only the students' learning behavior, but also the teaching strategies of their teachers.

The fundamental theoretical principles underlying the development of a model for scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of future teachers allow us to describe the technology behind this process. One of the organizational prerequisites for this support is the creation of a unified space for the exchange of scientific knowledge and practical experience in collaboration with educational organizations abroad. The proposed framework envisions the creation of a digital Russian-language linguodidactic educational environment that is both rich and open. This richness ensures the availability of a variety of information sources, reference books, teaching aids, audio and video materials, didactic materials, etc., intended for those receiving scientific and methodological support and compensating for the lack of a language environment. The proposed content, on the one hand, creates opportunities for students' intellectual development in accordance with their motives and needs, optimizing the process of mastering the Russian language. On the other hand, it ensures the effective teaching of Russian as a second language in a foreign educational environment by expanding, supplementing, and deepening the educational process with the necessary materials for the professional development of Russian language teachers. Openness contributes to the humanization of the educational space and the establishment of a comfortable psychological climate.

Scientific and methodological assistance is focused on the requests of educational entities, targeted work on the dissemination and implementation of educational and methodological products in the process of training future teachers of Russian as a second language.

We will illustrate, using specific examples, some digital educational environment resources, the design and development of which are strictly focused on the goals, objectives, and needs of the target audience. An important characteristic of the digital educational space is interactivity. The interactive educational course "Russia – Central Asian Republic: Dialogue of Cultures" is a multimedia complex that includes a variety of illustrative materials, assignments to develop grammar and phonetic skills, texts for reading and listening, and a linguistic and cultural commentary. All materials are intended for independent study and/or under the guidance of a teacher. Increasing the volume of learning activities through independent work performed by students will positively impact the acquisition of Russian as a second language.

The Russian language distance learning course "Welcome to the Russian World" introduces students to a diverse picture of Russian society and the realities and system of spiritual and moral values of the target language country. The structuring of the material, the selection of texts, and their differentiation are based on the principles of communicativeness and intercultural orientation. Understanding the meanings of another culture and acquiring cultural experience occurs through decoding and interpreting texts, which facilitates targeted preparation for real-life communication and productive dialogue, as well as the creation of creative works that convey an objective perception of our country abroad.

The scientific and methodological support technology aims to improve the quality of professional and pedagogical training for teachers of Russian as a second language, both in terms of enhancing their language proficiency and methodological skills. This assistance is provided in various formats: in-person and/or remotely, depending on the goals and educational needs of teachers in the partner country. This includes providing textbooks developed with an ethno-oriented methodology in mind and taking into account the specifics of teaching in a non-linguistic environment for English-, French-, and Spanish-speaking students.

It should be noted that the process of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of teachers of Russian as a second language, organized in accordance with the presented model, takes into account the specifics of the work and the professional needs of all participants in the educational process in the absence of an authentic language environment and presupposes continuous interaction between Russian and foreign philology teachers, thereby ensuring effective teaching of Russian in a foreign educational environment, professional development, self-

development, and self-actualization of both teachers and students, and future teachers of Russian as a second language. A new format of educational space is being created within the framework of curricular and extracurricular activities, promoting the perception of the world as a unified whole.

The proposed model of scientific and methodological support is a dynamic system for managing the process of training future teachers of Russian as a second language and allows for the implementation of: 1) deep immersion in the context of professional language education; 2) acquisition of knowledge about various spheres of life in the country of the studied language in the conditions of a non-linguistic environment; 3) mastery of the values and norms of the country of the studied language and solution of the problem of one's own identity; 4) mastery of strategies for a conscious attitude to educational activities; 5) improvement of the quality of professional language training of teachers of Russian as a second language.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results of this study confirm and complement a number of previous studies devoted to the scientific and methodological support of the educational process.

In analyzing existing approaches to defining scientific and methodological support for the educational process, we adhere to the viewpoint of M.A. Varzanova, who views it as both a process and a technology [7]. We agree with those researchers who define support for the foreign system of teaching Russian as continuous intercultural interaction between Russian and foreign professional communities of teachers, ensuring the conditions for the effective professional training of teachers of Russian as a second language in a non-linguistic environment [29].

This opinion is generally shared by researchers [13; 18], who have outlined ways to train competent teachers of Russian as a second language, taking into account the peculiarities of the second language learning environment when working in Russia and outside of Russia.

Our reflections on the functioning of the process of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of teachers of Russian as a second language fully coincide with the position of V.B. Tsarkova, who believes that only "turning to modeling will allow us to focus attention on the logical foundations of this process." [30].

The model is based on the results of experimental studies confirming the positive impact of scientific and methodological support on the cognitive, behavioral, and emotional engagement of students in the educational process [34]. Cognitive engagement, characterized by a strategic focus, self-regulation, and deep processing of information, helps students build logical and cause-and-effect relationships, stimulates the search for answers and solutions, and provides scope for ideas and creativity [35]. The teacher helps students develop their own position, increasing their activity, awareness, and responsibility in the process of acquiring knowledge [10; 11].

The findings of the above-mentioned researchers are fully consistent with our ideas about the scientific and methodological support of professional language training of teachers of Russian as a second language. The approach we propose intersects with the ideas of those modern researchers who point to the need to include autochthonous cultural values [36] and spiritual and moral values of the country of the studied language, which are sufficient to ensure the developmental, cognitive, educational and training nature of education [32]; the need to integrate innovative technologies in the professional language training of teachers, implemented in different formats [17]; the need for active interaction with the teacher and peers through the use of educational media resources through educational platforms [25]; the need to use applications and interactive multimedia tools for language learning [22]; the need to create a culturally inclusive and effective environment for learning a second language [36]; the need to use educational materials containing cultural values to promote intercultural competencies and communicative skills of students within the framework of multilingual education [37].

The proposed model of scientific and methodological support is based on intercultural, activity-based, communicative, and cognitive approaches and allows for the organization of professional language training for teachers in accordance with a wide range of key areas, within the framework of existing scientific schools and resource platforms of partner universities in a non-linguistic environment.

CONCLUSIONS

The conducted research allowed us to draw the following conclusions:

1. The problems of linguistic and scientific-pedagogical support for the professional language training of teachers of Russian as a second language in the context of digitalization of education must be addressed comprehensively at the socio-professional, innovative-methodological, scientific-technological and personal-motivational levels using advanced methods and technologies for teaching Russian as a second language and methods of its teaching.
2. For the effective functioning of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of teachers of Russian as a second language, the conceptual foundations of a model have been developed that reveals the methodological approaches, principles, conditions, and content of scientific and methodological support for the professional language training of teachers of Russian as a second language, similar in all respects to the proposed support process and meeting certain requirements.
3. The content block of the scientific and methodological support model is presented in digital and real format and has a number of important characteristics: interactivity, openness, richness, national and cultural conditioning, personal orientation.
4. The model is a dynamic system for managing the process of training future teachers of Russian as a second language and provides the basis for implementing a number of applied tasks: 1) deep immersion in the context of professional language education; 2) mastering knowledge about various spheres of life in the country of the studied language in the conditions of a non-linguistic environment; 3) mastering the values and norms of the country of the studied language and resolving the problem of one's own identity; 4) mastering strategies for a conscious attitude to educational activities; 5) improving the quality of professional language training of Russian language teachers.

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